

Med corals

GGG

7/18/2022

```
library(tidyverse)
```

```
## — Attaching packages — tidyverse 1.3.2 —
## ✓ ggplot2 3.4.0      ✓ purrr  1.0.1
## ✓ tibble  3.1.8      ✓ dplyr  1.1.0
## ✓ tidyr   1.3.0      ✓ stringr 1.5.0
## ✓ readr   2.1.3      ✓ forcats 1.0.0
## — Conflicts — tidyverse_conflicts() —
## * dplyr::filter() masks stats::filter()
## * dplyr::lag()    masks stats::lag()
```

```
library(readxl)
library(janitor)
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'janitor'
##
## The following objects are masked from 'package:stats':
##
##   chisq.test, fisher.test
```

```
library(dbplyr)
```

```
##
## Attaching package: 'dbplyr'
##
## The following objects are masked from 'package:dplyr':
##
##   ident, sql
```

Importing CSV file

```
med_wreck_corals <- read.csv("~/Documents/github/med_madracis/FIREData_Med2022_Annotate
d.csv")
head(med_wreck_corals)
```

```

## Species Colony Orientation File DATE TIME PAR Depth.m. T.C.
## 1 Oculina 1 up 20220718 7/18/22 35349 768.6 13.7 28.8
## 2 Oculina 1 up 20220718 7/18/22 35359 613.1 13.7 28.8
## 3 Oculina 1 up 20220718 7/18/22 35367 429.2 13.7 28.8
## 4 Oculina 1 up 20220718 7/18/22 35382 558.1 13.6 28.8
## 5 Oculina 1 up 20220718 7/18/22 35393 641.0 13.6 28.8
## 6 Oculina 2 up 20220718 7/18/22 35434 520.3 13.7 28.8
## Battery_V Dark_Fo Fm Fv Fv.Fm Sigma p Alp1 Tau1 Alp2 Tau2 Alp3
## 1 14.44 806.4 1191.4 385.1 0.323 473.4 0.05 0.60 1159 0.08 32807 0.32
## 2 14.44 814.9 1364.7 549.8 0.403 483.0 0.00 0.66 1025 0.09 28426 0.24
## 3 14.44 782.5 1424.3 641.8 0.451 529.4 0.06 0.69 957 0.10 25530 0.21
## 4 14.43 800.5 1347.6 547.1 0.406 502.3 0.01 0.69 1004 0.11 25270 0.20
## 5 14.43 767.6 1363.6 596.0 0.437 567.6 0.09 0.67 953 0.06 5114 0.27
## 6 14.42 933.0 1531.9 598.9 0.391 548.3 0.02 0.53 995 0.19 1544 0.28
## Tau3 Alp4 Tau4 TauAv1 TauAv2 GAIN Light_Fo Fm.1 Fv.1 Fv.Fm.1
## 1 50000 ----- ----- 4724 19149 0 1230.4 1360.9 130.5 0.096
## 2 50000 ----- ----- 4373 15521 0 1485.4 1658.8 173.4 0.105
## 3 50000 ----- ----- 3953 13770 0 1656.9 1848.2 191.3 0.104
## 4 50000 ----- ----- 4366 13591 0 1468.3 1654.5 186.2 0.113
## 5 50000 ----- ----- 1315 14369 0 1473.8 1648.5 174.7 0.106
## 6 50000 ----- ----- 1139 14767 0 1677.3 1863.6 186.3 0.100
## Sigma.1 p.1 Alp1.1 Tau1.1 Alp2.1 Tau2.1 Alp3.1 Tau3.1 Alp4.1 Tau4.1
## 1 231.8 0.00 0.499 1768 0.495 15961 0.006 50000 ----- -----
## 2 230.9 0.00 0.398 1661 0.597 14198 0.005 50000 ----- -----
## 3 218.8 0.00 0.275 1485 0.719 15581 0.006 50000 ----- -----
## 4 224.9 0.00 0.382 1570 0.613 14192 0.005 50000 ----- -----
## 5 287.1 0.01 0.440 1788 0.555 13051 0.005 50000 ----- -----
## 6 240.1 0.00 0.409 1661 0.586 13705 0.005 50000 ----- -----
## TauAv1.1 TauAv2.1 Pmax.e.s. Npq
## 1 8836 9067 113.2 1.950192
## 2 9186 9409 108.9 2.170704
## 3 11686 11918 85.6 2.354940
## 4 9351 9562 106.9 1.938238
## 5 8071 8299 123.9 2.411563
## 6 8756 8960 114.2 2.214707

```

Now averaging the replicate readings for each colony

```

med_wreck_colony <- med_wreck_corals %>% group_by(Species, Colony, Orientation) %>% summarise(
  avg_FvFm = mean(Fv.Fm), avg_p=mean(p), avg_Pmax = mean(Pmax.e.s.), avg_Sigma = mean(Sigma),
  avg_TauAv1=mean(TauAv1), avg_Npq = mean(Npq))

```

```

## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'Species', 'Colony'. You can override using
## the `.groups` argument.

```

```

head(med_wreck_colony)

```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 9
## # Groups:   Species, Colony [6]
##   Species  Colony Orientation avg_FvFm avg_p avg_Pmax avg_Sigma avg_T...1 avg_Npq
##   <chr>    <int> <chr>          <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 Cladocora 1 up          0.393 0         107.    495.    1566.    2.51
## 2 Cladocora 2 up          0.403 0.002     143.    438.    1587.    2.24
## 3 Cladocora 3 up          0.417 0.012     121.    429.    1546.    1.96
## 4 Cladocora 4 up          0.428 0.022     102.    548.    1904.    3.02
## 5 Cladocora 5 up          0.424 0.006     106.    505.    1715.    2.48
## 6 Cladocora 6 up          0.436 0.008     122.    525.    1923.    2.71
## # ... with abbreviated variable name 1avg_TauAv1
```

And now making a graph of the 3 variables

```
FvFm_plot <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_colony, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_FvFm, fill = Species)) + geom_boxplot() + labs(y = "Mean FvFm", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
FvFm_plot
```



```
Pmax_plot <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_colony, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_Pmax, fill = Species)) + geom_boxplot() + labs(y = "Mean Pmax", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
Pmax_plot
```



```
P_plot <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_colony, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_p, fill = Species)) + geom_boxplot() + labs(y = "Mean p", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
P_plot
```



```
med_wreck_madracis <- med_wreck_colony %>% filter(Species=="Madracis")
head(med_wreck_madracis)
```

```
## # A tibble: 6 × 9
## # Groups:   Species, Colony [6]
##   Species Colony Orientation avg_FvFm avg_p avg_Pmax avg_Sigma avg_Ta...1 avg_Npq
##   <chr>      <int> <chr>      <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1 Madracis     1 side      0.404 0.152   96.8   580.  2064   1.98
## 2 Madracis     2 side      0.443 0.152  103.   540.  2179.   2.50
## 3 Madracis     3 side      0.496 0.106  112.   474.  2504.   2.47
## 4 Madracis     4 side      0.457 0.12   105.   468.  2640.   2.14
## 5 Madracis     5 side      0.390 0.078  113.   556.  2290.   2.03
## 6 Madracis     6 down      0.479 0.07   107.   465.  3217.   2.47
## # ... with abbreviated variable name 1avg_TauAv1
```

```
Npq_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_Npq)) + geo
m_boxplot(fill = "indianred4") + labs(y = "Mean NPq", x = "Orientation") +theme_classic
() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 1
2)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), a
xis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
Npq_plot_mad
```



```
FvFm_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_FvFm)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = "orchid4") + labs(y = "Mean Fv'Fm'", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() +
  theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) +
  theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14),
  axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1)) + scale_x_discrete(labels = c("dark", "light"))
FvFm_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_FvFm.eps", plot = FvFm_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps", width = 8, height = 6, dpi = 600)
```

```
Sigma_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_Sigma)) +
  geom_boxplot(fill = "plum") + labs(y = "Mean Functional Absorption", x = "Orientation")
+theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12))
+ theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
+ scale_x_discrete(labels = c("dark", "light"))
Sigma_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_Sigma.eps", plot = Sigma_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/githu
b/med_madracis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
Pmax_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_Pmax)) + g
eom_boxplot(fill = "mistyroze") + labs(y = "Mean Pmax", x = "Orientation") +theme_classi
c() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 1
2)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), a
xis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))+ scale_x_discrete(labels = c("dark", "li
ght"))
Pmax_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_Pmax.eps", plot = Pmax_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
p_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_p)) + geom_boxplot(fill = "lightsalmon1") + labs(y = "Mean Connectivity Parameter", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))+ scale_x_discrete(labels = c("dark", "light"))
p_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_Connectivity.eps", plot = p_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
Tau_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(x = Orientation, y=avg_TauAv1)) +  
geom_boxplot(fill = "indianred") + labs(y = "Mean rate of electron transfer", x = "Orientation") +  
theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text =  
element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title =  
element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))+ scale_x_discrete(l  
abels = c("dark", "light"))  
Tau_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_Electron_Transfer.eps", plot = Tau_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps", width = 8, height = 6, dpi = 600)
```

```
shapiro.test(med_wreck_madracis$avg_FvFm)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: med_wreck_madracis$avg_FvFm  
## W = 0.97391, p-value = 0.8826
```

```
ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes((((avg_FvFm)))) + geom_histogram()
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```



```
qqnorm(med_wreck_madracis$avg_FvFm)
```

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
shapiro.test(sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_Pmax)))
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_Pmax))  
## W = 0.81392, p-value = 0.003169
```

```
ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(sqrt(sqrt(avg_Pmax)))) + geom_histogram()
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```



```
qqnorm(sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_Pmax)))
```

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
shapiro.test(sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_p)))
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data:  sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_p))  
## W = 0.91433, p-value = 0.1184
```

```
ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(sqrt(sqrt(avg_p)))) + geom_histogram()
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```



```
qqnorm(sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_p)))
```

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
shapiro.test(med_wreck_madracis$avg_Sigma)
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: med_wreck_madracis$avg_Sigma  
## W = 0.94632, p-value = 0.4009
```

```
qqnorm(sqrt(log(med_wreck_madracis$avg_Sigma)))
```

Normal Q-Q Plot


```
ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(sqrt(log(avg_Sigma)))) + geom_histogram()
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```



```
shapiro.test(med_wreck_madracis$avg_TauAv1)
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data: med_wreck_madracis$avg_TauAv1
## W = 0.94912, p-value = 0.4428
```

```
ggplot(data = med_wreck_madracis, aes(sqrt(sqrt(sqrt((avg_TauAv1))))) + geom_histogram
())
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```



```
qqnorm(sqrt(sqrt(sqrt(med_wreck_madracis$avg_TauAv1))))
```

Normal Q-Q Plot

All normal except for Pmax

```
FvFm_anova <- aov((avg_FvFm) ~ (Orientation), data = med_wreck_madracis)
summary.aov(FvFm_anova)
```

```
##           Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## Orientation  1 0.001101 0.001101   0.821  0.379
## Residuals  15 0.020105 0.001340
```

```
p_anova <- aov(sqrt(sqrt(avg_p)) ~ (Orientation), data = med_wreck_madracis)
summary.aov(p_anova)
```

```
##           Df  Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## Orientation  1 0.01522 0.015216   6.87 0.0193 *
## Residuals  15 0.03322 0.002215
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
Sigma_anova <- aov(sqrt(log(avg_Sigma)) ~ (Orientation), data = med_wreck_madracis)
summary.aov(Sigma_anova)
```

```
##           Df  Sum Sq  Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## Orientation  1 0.000012 0.0000122  0.025  0.876
## Residuals   15 0.007293 0.0004862
```

```
Tau_anova <- aov(sqrt(sqrt(sqrt(avg_TauAv1))) ~ (Orientation), data = med_wreck_madracis)
summary.aov(Tau_anova)
```

```
##           Df  Sum Sq  Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## Orientation  1 0.00218 0.002176  0.308  0.587
## Residuals   15 0.10612 0.007075
```

```
Pmax_Kruskal <- kruskal.test(avg_Pmax ~ Orientation, data = med_wreck_madracis)
Pmax_Kruskal
```

```
##
## Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test
##
## data:  avg_Pmax by Orientation
## Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 0.4, df = 1, p-value = 0.5271
```

```
med_wreck_zoox <- read.csv("~/Documents/github/med_madracis/med_zoox_revised.csv")
head(med_wreck_zoox)
```

```
##   sample orientation Chl_a_ug_ml Protein_mg_ml Protein_ug_ml density_cells_ml
## 1      1      dark 0.061379533    0.7339876      733.9876      160000.00
## 2      2      dark 0.007852167    0.4124714      412.4714       53333.33
## 3      3      dark 0.048165500    0.8029444      802.9444         0.00
## 4      4      dark 0.069825667    0.3545139      354.5139      373333.33
## 5      5      dark 0.000000000    0.2999408      299.9408      106666.67
## 6      6     light 0.311420200    0.1493358      149.3358      1973333.33
##   density_cells_ug_protein  chl_a_zoox  chl_a_ug_protein
## 1          217.9873 3.83622e-07    0.0000836247
## 2          129.3019 1.47228e-07    0.0000190369
## 3           0.0000 0.00000e+00    0.0000599861
## 4         1053.0851 1.87033e-07    0.0001969620
## 5           355.6258 0.00000e+00    0.0000000000
## 6        13214.0661 1.57814e-07    0.0020853680
```

```
zoox_den_plot <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_zoox, aes(x = orientation, y=density_cells_ug_p
rotein)) + geom_boxplot(fill = "turquoise3") + labs(y = "Mean Zooxanthellae density (cel
ls/ug protein)", x = "Orientation") +theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text
(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(siz
e = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hj
ust=1))
zoox_den_plot
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Madracis_Zooxanthellae_den.eps", plot = zoox_den_plot, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
zoox_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_zoox, aes(x = orientation, y=log(density_cells_ml))) + geom_boxplot(fill = "turquoise3") + labs(y = "Log Mean Zoox Density", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
zoox_plot_mad
```

```
## Warning: Removed 1 rows containing non-finite values (`stat_boxplot()`).
```



```
shapiro.test(log(med_wreck_zoox$density_cells_ug_protein+1))
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  log(med_wreck_zoox$density_cells_ug_protein + 1)
## W = 0.89317, p-value = 0.1841
```

```
zoox_den_anova <- aov(log(density_cells_ug_protein+1) ~ (orientation), data = med_wreck_
zoox)
summary.aov(zoox_den_anova)
```

```
##           Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## orientation  1  44.18   44.18   9.972 0.0134 *
## Residuals    8  35.45    4.43
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
chla_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_zoox, aes(x = orientation, y=(chla_ug_protein))) + geom_boxplot(fill = "aquamarine3") + labs(y = "Mean Chl_a Density (ug Chla/ug protein)", x = "Orientation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
chla_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Chlorophyll_protein.eps", plot = chla_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madraxis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
shapiro.test(sqrt(med_wreck_zoox$chla_ug_protein))
```

```
##
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test
##
## data:  sqrt(med_wreck_zoox$chla_ug_protein)
## W = 0.88074, p-value = 0.1331
```

```
chla_den_anova <- aov(sqrt(chla_ug_protein) ~ (orientation), data = med_wreck_zoox)
summary.aov(chla_den_anova)
```

```
##           Df  Sum Sq  Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)
## orientation 1 0.001586 0.0015858   10.44  0.012 *
## Residuals   8 0.001216 0.0001519
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
```

```
chla_zoox_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_zoox, aes(x = orientation, y=(chla_zoox)))
+ geom_boxplot(fill = "aquamarine4") + labs(y = "Mean Chl_a per Zooxanthellae", x = "Orientation")
+ theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text = element_text(size = 12))
+ theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))
chla_zoox_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "Chlorophyll_density_zoox.eps", plot = chla_zoox_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps", width = 8, height = 6, dpi = 600)
```

```
shapiro.test((med_wreck_zoox$chla_zoox))
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: (med_wreck_zoox$chla_zoox)  
## W = 0.88392, p-value = 0.1447
```

```
chla_zoox_anova <- aov((chla_zoox) ~ (orientation), data = med_wreck_zoox)  
summary.aov(chla_zoox_anova)
```

```
##           Df      Sum Sq  Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)  
## orientation  1 1.700e-15 1.701e-15  0.127  0.73  
## Residuals   8 1.067e-13 1.334e-14
```

```
protein_plot_mad <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_zoox, aes(x = orientation, y=(Protein_ug_m  
l))) + geom_boxplot(fill = "paleturquoise") + labs(y = "Mean Protein (ug/ml)", x = "Orie  
ntation") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 14), legend.text =  
element_text(size = 12)) + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = eleme  
nt_text(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1))  
protein_plot_mad
```



```
ggsave(filename = "protein_density_ml.eps", plot = protein_plot_mad, path = "~/Documents/github/med_madracis", device = "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)
```

```
shapiro.test((med_wreck_zoox$Protein_ug_ml))
```

```
##  
## Shapiro-Wilk normality test  
##  
## data: (med_wreck_zoox$Protein_ug_ml)  
## W = 0.8637, p-value = 0.08435
```

```
protein_anova <- aov((Protein_ug_ml) ~ (orientation), data = med_wreck_zoox)  
summary.aov(protein_anova)
```

```
##           Df Sum Sq Mean Sq F value Pr(>F)  
## orientation 1 106901  106901   1.856   0.21  
## Residuals   8 460836   57605
```

```
med_wreck_symbiont <- read.csv("~/Documents/github/med_madracis/symbiont_data.csv")  
head(med_wreck_symbiont)
```

##	sample_name	Clade.A	Clade.B	Clade.C	A1bo	A1dv	A1	A1dl	A1fb	X1267698_A	
## 1	light_4	0	7727	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	
## 2	light_5	186	4206	0	0	1656	4411	1495	0	0	
## 3	light_8	7	838	0	1533	0	0	0	0	0	
## 4	light_6	327	7644	26	2886	15	597	0	0	0	
## 5	dark_3	15	19	0	2139	1232	0	0	181	0	
## 6	dark_1	1886	0	662	3521	1017	2050	0	1657	1886	
##	X1266819_A	A1dw	A1ml	A1jd	X1933304_A	X1838_A	X445284_A	X2837538_A	X293385_A		
## 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
## 2	0	1892	166	675	0	89	0	0	0		
## 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
## 4	0	0	77	0	0	20	0	215	0		
## 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15		
## 6	0	0	82	0	0	0	0	0	0		
##	X442096_A	X221869_A	X3528_A	X53810_A	X969_A	X1580099_A	X1580100_A	X1581951_A			
## 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
## 2	0	0	52	0	45	0	0	0			
## 3	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0			
## 4	0	0	21	16	0	21	18	16			
## 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
## 6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
##	B2	B19w	B2b	B2ao	B2an	B2c	B2t	B19o	X46264_B	X46263_B	X1157325_B
## 1	80511	12999	15427	10319	4220	8063	3607	2385	4227	1449	2051
## 2	50860	6389	2587	0	3793	6875	2483	2523	0	792	1147
## 3	5280	1447	1455	430	511	514	424	67	167	151	116
## 4	40376	2628	4714	7794	6735	6478	3959	2407	2795	3095	1135
## 5	1139	12	0	961	0	0	641	0	0	0	19
## 6	0	0	0	0	2496	0	0	0	0	0	0
##	X3113936_B	B2x	X1390079_B	C21eh	C21	X121775_C	X38759_C	X38770_C	C72	C21az	
## 1	0	1061	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
## 2	1715	535	552	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
## 3	404	130	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
## 4	619	2112	0	133	0	0	0	0	0	0	
## 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
## 6	0	0	0	0	748	0	0	0	0	0	
##	C21cv	X108587_C	X345189_C	X147903_C	X3113945_C	X3113940_C	X3113937_C				
## 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	16				
## 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 6	179	263	0	0	142	0	0				
##	X3113941_C	X3113942_C	X3113943_C	X3113946_C	X3113944_C	X16792_C	X3113947_C				
## 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 6	0	0	0	40	0	0	29				
##	X108803_C	X108259_C	X51681_C	X3113948_C	X3113949_C	X3113950_C	X3113953_C				
## 1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
## 2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				

```
## 3      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 4      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 5      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 6     28      0     25     18     15     14     11
## X3113952_C X3113951_C X3113954_C X3113957_C X3113956_C X3113955_C X3113960_C
## 1      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 2      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 3      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 4      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 5      0      0      0      0      0      0      0
## 6     11     11     10      8      8      8      7
## X3113959_C X3113958_C X3113938_C X3113939_C
## 1      0      0      0      0
## 2      0      0      0      0
## 3      0      0      0      0
## 4      0      0      6      4
## 5      0      0      0      0
## 6      7      7      0      0
```

```
med_wreck_heatmap <- read.csv("~/Documents/github/med_madracis/symbiont_data_heatmap.csv")
head(med_wreck_heatmap)
```

```
## sample.name clade avg.clade number
## 1 light_4 Clade A A 0
## 2 light_4 Clade B B 7727
## 3 light_4 Clade C C 0
## 4 light_4 A1bo A1 0
## 5 light_4 A1dv A1 0
## 6 light_4 A1 A1 9
```

```
frequency <- med_wreck_heatmap %>% group_by(sample.name, avg.clade) %>% summarise(total = sum(number))
```

```
## `summarise()` has grouped output by 'sample.name'. You can override using the
## `.groups` argument.
```

```
ggplot(data = frequency, aes(x = sample.name, y = total, fill = avg.clade)) + geom_bar(stat = "summary", fun.y = "mean", position = "fill", color = "black") + labs(y = "Relative Abundance", x = "Orientation", fill = "Symbiont Clade") + theme_classic() + theme(legend.title = element_text(size = 12, face = "bold"), legend.text = element_text(size = 8), legend.position = "right") + scale_fill_discrete() + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text(size = 14)) + scale_fill_manual(values = c("darkseagreen2", "mediumseagreen", "lightskyblue1", "steelblue2", "dodgerblue3", "plum1", "mediumpurple1", "purple3"))
```

```
## Warning in geom_bar(stat = "summary", fun.y = "mean", position = "fill", :
## Ignoring unknown parameters: `fun.y`
```

```
## Scale for fill is already present.
## Adding another scale for fill, which will replace the existing scale.
## No summary function supplied, defaulting to `mean_se()`
```



```
ggsave(filename = "symbionts_mad.eps", path = "~/Documents/github/Med_madracis", device = "eps", width = 8, height = 6, dpi = 600)
```

```
## No summary function supplied, defaulting to `mean_se()`
```

```
med_wreck_sem <- read.csv("~/Documents/github/med_madracis/Madracis_SEM.csv")
head(med_wreck_sem)
```

```
## treatment Category Size
## 1 light calyx_width 1406.935
## 2 light calyx_width 1342.972
## 3 light calyx_width 1611.866
## 4 light calyx_width 1598.639
## 5 light calyx_width 2401.618
## 6 light calyx_width 2200.054
```

```

sem_treatment <- c(calyx_width = "Calyx", centre_width = "Center", septa_width = "Septa")
sem_plot <- ggplot(data = med_wreck_sem, aes(x = treatment, y=Size, fill = Category)) +
  geom_boxplot() + labs(y = "Length (mm)", x = "Orientation") + theme_bw() + theme(legend.p
osition = "none") + theme(axis.text = element_text(size = 12), axis.title = element_text
(size = 14), axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust=1)) + facet_wrap(.~Category, s
cales = "free", labeller = labeller(Category = sem_treatment)) + scale_fill_brewer(palet
te = "Set2")
sem_plot

```



```

ggsave(filename = "sem_mad_light.eps", path = "~/Documents/github/Med_madracis", device
= "eps",width = 8,height = 6,dpi = 600)

```